

A numerical scheme for the thermodynamic analysis of gas turbines

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Abstract

In this work we present a numerical scheme for the steady-state thermodynamic analysis of gas turbine engines. As usual in the literature, **it is based on modelling the gas turbine as a set of independent components connected through nodes**, thus giving the user great flexibility to modify the gas turbine's model and to define and include new components. Additionally, the proposed method provides the same flexibility for the inclusion of new gas properties calculators and nonlinear equations solvers. The simulator also allows identifying the characteristic parameters of the different components of the gas turbine —such as the compressor's nominal pressure ratio and efficiency— from a batch of operation data. The latter task is accomplished by means of a systematic and computationally economic procedure which allows that the parameters identification be performed component-by-component and does not require any full gas turbine simulations. The scheme has been formulated so that it exploits the full capabilities of today's computers and mathematical techniques —such as sparse matrix solvers and quasi-Newton methods for sparse jacobians— but, at the same time, remains simple enough to be self-implemented by the interested researchers with the aid of general-purpose mathematical computing software such as Matlab. The simulator has been applied to predict the performance of a real gas turbine, obtaining excellent results.

Keywords: gas turbine simulation, multicomponent modelling, off-design performance prediction, parameters estimation

1 List of Symbols

2	α	Opening position of a valve
3	$\bar{\gamma}$	Mean value of γ in a component
4	β	First auxiliary coordinate of the compressor's map
5		
6	η	Polytropic efficiency
7	γ	Adiabatic constant
8	μ	$= m\sqrt{T}/p$ corrected mass flow rate
9	ν	Second auxiliary coordinate of the compressor's map
10		
11	W^*	Total power output
12	c_p	Specific heat at constant pressure
13	c_v	Specific heat at constant volume

14	h	Specific enthalpy
15	K_t	Turbine choke constant
16	m	Mass flow rate
17	N	Regime speed
18	p	Pressure
19	s	Specific entropy
20	T	Temperature
21	u	Specific internal energy
22	W	Power
23	x_A	Mass fraction of species A
24	y_A	Molar fraction of species A
25	EGT	Exhaust gas temperature
26	I2D	Independent-to-dependent subroutine
27	IBH	Inlet bleed heating circuit
28	IGV	Inlet guide vanes
29	PR	Pressure ratio
30	TIT	Turbine inlet temperature
31	λ^*	Cell of parameters of the I2D subroutine
32	λ	Cell of parameters of the component
33	\mathcal{S}	Cell of species

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34	0	Null matrix
35	f^{all}	Vector with the residuals of all the compo-
36		nents and general boundary conditions
37	f^{gbc}	Vector with the residuals of a certain gen-
38		eral boundary condition
39	f	Residual of a component
40	I	Identity matrix
41	v^{out}	Cell with the tags of the output variables of
42		the I2D subroutine
43	W	Weighting matrix
44	x^{all}	Vector with the independent and the depen-
45		dent variables
46	x^{dep}	Vector of dependent variables
47	x^{gbc}	Vector of fixed boundary conditions
48	x^{ind}	Vector of independent variables
49	xⁱⁿ	Vector of input variables of the I2D subrou-
50		tine
51	x^{nod}	Vector of nodal variables
52	x^{out}	Vector of output variables of the I2D sub-
53		routine
54	x^{unk}	Vector of unknowns
55	Subscripts	
56	0	Nominal value
57	c	Compressor
58	t	Turbine

59 1. Introduction

60 Gas turbine engines have been widely used over
61 the last decades in the fields of electric power gen-
62 eration and aircraft and shift propulsion [1, 2]. As
63 a consequence, and also due to the increasing com-
64 plexity of gas turbine configurations and optimiza-
65 tion strategies, there is a huge interest nowadays
66 on efficient and accurate computational approaches
67 for their thermodynamic analysis. In effect, numeri-
68 cal modelling allows, e.g., for the design and opti-
69 mization of new configurations [3, 4], for off-design
70 performance prediction [2, 3, 5], for health monitor-
71 ing [6–8], for real-time simulation and control tasks
72 [9] and for the identification of the parameters of
73 the gas turbine components from experimental data
74 [10]. This fact has motivated the development of
75 several simulation programs such as DNA [11, 12],
76 GasTurb [13], GSP [14–16], CycleTempo [17] and
77 CAMEL [18], among others [19–27] —refer to the
78 surveys by Elmegaard and Houbak [28] and by As-
79 gari et al. [29]—.

80 In general, the simulation programs provide a
81 component library so that the user can choose the
82 pieces of equipment that integrate the gas turbine

83 and the way they are interconnected, making thus
84 analysis greatly flexible. It should be noted, how-
85 ever, that many of these programs [13, 16, 17, 20–
86 22, 30] are only accessible under a commercial li-
87 cense, have a high learning cost and are relatively
88 rigid with respect to the inclusion of custom compo-
89 nents to the library (since this is not permitted or
90 requires some detailed knowledge about the code’s
91 architecture). Some others [18, 23–26] are easily ac-
92 cessible to researchers and can be self-implemented,
93 but were developed many years ago and do not ex-
94 ploit the full capabilities of today’s computers and
95 mathematical techniques —such as sparse matrix
96 solvers and quasi-Newton methods—. The latter
97 drawback is also present —to a smaller extent— in
98 some more modern programs [17, 20–22, 30] that
99 solve the whole set of equations of the model in a
100 sequential way, when it could be easier and more ef-
101 ficient to solve them simultaneously [31]. Whereas
102 this problem is avoided by some other modern pro-
103 grams such as [11, 13, 16], in many cases it is not
104 possible to choose the equations solver.

105 The latter point concerning the (iterative) equa-
106 tions solver is crucial for the efficiency of the simula-
107 tor but, in our opinion, has received little attention
108 in the literature. In fact, the Newton-Raphson al-
109 gorithm, which is the most frequently used method,
110 requires the computation of the jacobian of the
111 equations system at each iteration, which is pre-
112 cisely the most expensive task [31]. Instead, some
113 of the so-called quasi-Newton methods —such as
114 the Schubert’s one [32]—, which minimize the num-
115 ber of required evaluations of the jacobian, could be
116 more appropriate for the case of power plant simu-
117 lation. Since the field of quasi-Newton methods is
118 currently being the focus of an extensive research
119 [33], it would be interesting to give the user flexibil-
120 ity also to choose a solver from an easily extensible
121 library.

122 Additionally, the parameters describing the par-
123 ticular behavior of the components installed in the
124 target power plant —e.g., the compressor nominal
125 efficiency— are not usually known. Therefore, the
126 implementation into the simulation tool of proce-
127 dures specifically designed to estimate component
128 parameters from operation data would be most de-
129 sirable. The approach considered in this work is
130 based on minimizing an objective function with op-
131 timization algorithms, as shown in [7, 10, 34], al-
132 though here the objective function has been formul-
133 ated so that (i) its evaluation does not require that
134 a full gas turbine simulation be performed and (ii)

135 it allows a component-by-component parameter's
 136 identification, instead of having to compute the pa-
 137 rameters of all the components at once. These two
 138 characteristics considerably simplify and accelerate
 139 the optimization search procedure.

140 Finally, it is important to note that most of the
 141 programs use an embedded thermodynamics prop-
 142 erties model, so that there is no flexibility to choose
 143 or to implement another one that could be more
 144 suitable for different purposes (low computational
 145 cost, high accuracy... depending on the particular
 146 case).

147 Taking into account all these considerations, a
 148 novel scheme for steady-state, gas turbine simula-
 149 tion has been developed in this work. **As many
 150 other programs, the proposed method is based on
 151 modelling the gas turbine as a set of individual com-
 152 ponents interconnected through nodes, each com-
 153 ponent being described by a set of equations that
 154 depend on the variables defined at the nodes. This
 155 modular methodology provides great flexibility for
 156 the study of different gas turbine configurations
 157 and for the inclusion of new components to the
 158 model. However, the method proposed in this work
 159 has been specifically designed to adequately fulfill
 160 a number of requirements: (i) a simpler formula-
 161 tion, so that the method can be easily implemented
 162 by the interested researchers with the aid of gen-
 163 eral-purpose mathematical computing software as
 164 Matlab, (ii) more flexibility for the computation of
 165 the thermodynamic properties, in a way that any
 166 specialized library such as Cantera [35] or REF-
 167 PROP [36] can be called from the main program,
 168 (iii) the possibility of choosing the solver from an
 169 extendable library instead of having to use one em-
 170 bedded within the main program, and (iv) a sys-
 171 tematic and computationally economic procedure
 172 to identify the components' parameters from ex-
 173 perimental data.**

174 The paper is structured as follows. First, some
 175 general definitions and concepts are introduced in
 176 section 2. Then, the main subroutines in which the
 177 code is fundamented are presented in section 3, the
 178 simulation scheme is detailed in section 4 and the
 179 algorithm for the components' parameters identifi-
 180 cation is explained in section 5. After that, the
 181 method is applied in section 6 to the case of a real
 182 gas turbine and the results are compared against
 183 the experimental data. Finally, the conclusions and
 184 some possible future works are discussed in section
 185 7.

186 2. General definitions and concepts

187 For the sake of clarity, we will introduce first
 188 some concepts prior to the explanation of the sim-
 189 ulation and parameters identification algorithms.

190 2.1. Components, nodes and types of nodes

191 As an introductory example, let us consider the
 192 gas turbine model shown in figure 1, which is consti-
 193 tuted by four parts or *components*: (i) a compres-
 194 sor with inlet guide vanes (IGV) whose operation map
 195 is described by two auxiliary, non-physical coordi-
 196 nates β and ν (see Appendix A), (ii) a combus-
 197 tion chamber, (iii) an expansion turbine and (iv) a
 198 power meter, which is a virtual component used to
 199 calculate the shaft power output from the power ab-
 200 sorbed by the compressor and the power extracted
 201 by the turbine. We will assume in this work that a
 202 component can be represented by a set of equations
 203 which do not depend on the presence of any other
 204 components.

Figure 1: Scheme of a simple gas turbine.

205 Each component possesses terminals or *nodes*, at
 206 which some variables of interest will be estimated,
 207 such as mass flow rate, pressure, valve's opening
 208 position or power, among many other possibilities,
 209 the user being able to introduce new variables in
 210 a new component if desired. The nodes can be
 211 used to interconnect the components, so that two or
 212 more components that share a node will also share
 213 the variables defined at it. Each node is identified
 214 by a single number defined by the user. **As shown
 215 in figure 1, the numbering employed in our case is
 216 not consecutive, but associates the first digit of the
 217 node numbers with the different components (e.g.,**

2* for the compressor²). This procedure facilitates the representation of more complex systems and the addition of new components.

In order to prevent failures derived from an improper assembling of the components, it is convenient to classify the nodes into *types*, so that nodes belonging to different types are not allowed to be interconnected. In the case shown in figure 1, for example, we have *gas-type* nodes—those that represent gas flow (20, 30, 31, 40, 41)—, *power-type* nodes—where power and regime speed are measured (50, 51, 52)— a *valve-type* node—associated to the opening position of a valve (26)— and an *auxiliary-type* node—associated to the auxiliary coordinates β and ν of the compressor’s map (27)—

2.2. Kinds of variables

We will assume that, in the example above, the fuel is composed of CH_4 and C_2H_6 , that there are no unburned hydrocarbons at the exhaust and that the gas through the turbine is composed of O_2 , N_2 , CO_2 and H_2O . These assumptions are made for simplicity, being possible to define more species in the simulator if desired. Then, as can be deduced from the equations of the different components (derived in Appendix A), the variables that need to be defined at each node are those shown in table 1.

Nodes	Variables
20,30,40,41	$m, p, T, \gamma, h, x_{\text{O}_2}, x_{\text{N}_2}, x_{\text{CO}_2}, x_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$
26	α
27	β, ν
31	$m, h, x_{\text{CH}_4}, x_{\text{C}_2\text{H}_6}$
50,52	W, N
51	W

Table 1: Variables defined at each node.

However, not all of the variables shown in table 1 are independent between each other. For instance, the thermodynamic variables are related through a gas model, which can be relatively simple—e.g., ideal gas— or more complex—e.g., derived from the NASA coefficients [37, 38]—. Thus, it is convenient to separate the variables in two groups: dependent and independent ones. The *independent*

variables are those that are not computed from any others defined in the same node, such as power and regime speed or, in the case of a gas-type node, mass flow rate, species’ mass or molar fractions and a coherent couple of thermodynamic variables—(h, s) or (p, T)—. The *dependent variables*, on the other hand, are those that are obtained from the independent ones through adequate models, as it happens with the rest of thermodynamic variables.

Note that the division between variables is not completely defined until several coherent thermodynamic variables per gas-type node are chosen as independent—e.g., p, T and the species’ mass fractions, or h, s and the species’ molar fractions—. This election depends on the employed gas properties calculator: some ones require predetermined variables to compute the rest, whereas some others [35] let the user select a consistent set of independent variables. Hence, the final list of dependent and independent variables of the gas turbine model relies on the gas properties model used. However, we can make another convenient classification of variables that does not depend on the latter. On the one hand, the *always-independent variables* are those that can never be computed from any other variables in the same node, such as mass flow rate, and thus will always be independent, regardless of the gas model. On the other hand, the *potentially dependent variables*, such as mass and molar fractions, pressure, temperature and other thermodynamic ones, which will finally be classified into dependent or independent variables by the employed gas model.

Table 2 shows the different kinds of variables at each node for the example considered in 1, and for the two classifications considered.

2.3. Groups of variables

With a view to make the method more flexible and to allow for other kinds of relationships apart from thermodynamic ones, it is convenient to divide the potentially dependent variables into independent sets, so that those belonging to different sets are not interrelated between them. These sets will be called as *groups*. For example, all the thermodynamic variables are interrelated between them through a gas model, and hence they form a group that will be named “gas group”:

$$\text{gas group} = \{p, T, h, s, u, \rho, \gamma, c_p, c_v, \dots\}.$$

Another possible group that could be of interest, especially for models based on statistics—although

²The compressor is numbered with 2*, and not with 1*, to make the notation consistent with that of a more complex example to be described later.

Node	Always independent	Potentially dependent	Independent	Dependent
20,30,40,41	m	$p, T, \gamma, h, x_{O_2}, x_{N_2}, x_{CO_2}, x_{H_2O}$	$m, p, T, x_{O_2}, x_{N_2}, x_{CO_2}, x_{H_2O}$	γ, h
26	α		α	
27	β, ν		β, ν	
31	m	$h, x_{CH_4}, x_{C_2H_6}$	$m, p, T, x_{CH_4}, x_{C_2H_6}$	h
50,52	W, N		W, N	
51	W		W	

Table 2: Kinds of variables at each node. In the right column, thermodynamic properties are classified as independent or dependent for the particular case of choosing p, T and the species' mass fractions to describe the thermodynamic state of the gas.

303 it is not the case of this work—, is the one com- 335
304 prising the statistical parameters of a random vari- 336
305 able Z : its instantaneous value z , the corresponding 337
306 density and distribution functions, $f(z)$ and $F(z)$, 338
307 respectively, and the values of the statistical mo- 339
308 ments $E[Z]$, $E[Z^2]$, etc. Indeed, in the case of a 340
309 normal distribution, for example, if z , $E[Z]$ and 341
310 $E[Z^2]$ are given, then $f(z)$, $F(z)$ and any statisti- 342
311 cal moment are known. Thus, these variables are 343
312 mutually dependent, but are not related to the ther- 344
313 modynamic variables, so they can be included in a 345
314 different group called “stats group”:

$$\text{stats group} = \{z, f(z), F(z), E[Z], E[Z^2], \dots\}.$$

315 For brevity, sometimes we will refer only to the “gas 348
316 group” and to gas models but, if needed, the “stats 349
317 group” and statistical models can be treated in the 350
318 same way. 351

319 2.4. Kinds of boundary conditions 348

320 Finally, the boundary conditions are divided in 349
321 two classes: *fixed* and *general*. *Fixed* boundary 350
322 conditions are those that impose a determined value for 351
323 an independent variable of the model, e.g., pres- 352
324 sure at node 20 (see figure 1) equals ambient pres- 353
325 sure. *General* ones are those boundary conditions 354
326 that involve more complex restrictions between any 355
327 number of variables and any number of nodes, e.g., 356
328 a control law of the form $f(\alpha_{26}, m_{31}, T_{40}) = 0$ be- 357
329 tween the opening position of the IGV (α_{26}), the 358
330 fuel mass flow rate (m_{31}) and the turbine inlet tem- 359
331 perature (T_{40}). 360
361

332 3. Main subroutines of the code 348

333 In this section we briefly describe the principal 349
334 subroutines that are invoked by the schemes that 350

335 carry out the simulation of the gas turbine perfor- 348
336 mance and the estimation of the components' pa- 349
337 rameters from a batch of operation data. 350

338 3.1. Component's residual 348

339 Every component in the library has a *residual* 348
340 *subroutine* used to calculate in each iteration the 349
341 residuals of the equations that describe it. As in- 350
342 put data, those subroutines receive a column vector 351
343 \mathbf{x}^{nod} containing the values of the variables at its 352
344 nodes (*vector of nodal variables*) and a cell array, 353
345 $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$, with the parameters that characterize the com- 354
346 ponent. For example, in the case of the considered 355
347 expansion turbine (see Appendix A) 356

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x}^{\text{nod}} &= [m_1, p_1, T_1, \gamma_1, h_1, (x_{O_2})_1, (x_{N_2})_1, \dots \\ &\quad (x_{H_2O})_1, (x_{CO_2})_1, m_2, p_2, T_2, \gamma_2, h_2, \dots \\ &\quad (x_{O_2})_2, (x_{N_2})_2, (x_{H_2O})_2, (x_{CO_2})_2, W_3]^T, \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda} &= \{K_t, \eta_t, \boldsymbol{\mathcal{S}}\}, \end{aligned}$$

348 where the subindex i refers to the i -th node of the 349
349 component³ and $\boldsymbol{\mathcal{S}}$ is another cell containing the 350
350 names of the species of the gas through the compo- 351
351 nent. 352

352 The first output of these subroutines is a vec- 353
353 tor, $\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}^{\text{nod}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})$, with the residuals of the equa- 354
354 tions that characterize the component, that is, \mathbf{f} is defined so that $\mathbf{f} = \mathbf{0}$ when \mathbf{x}^{nod} 355
355 and $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ verify those equations. Optionally, the sub- 356
356 routine can provide a second output with the jaco- 357
357 bian of the residuals with respect to the nodal 358
358 variables, i.e., the matrix $\partial \mathbf{f} / \partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{nod}}$, which is some- 359
359 times required by the equations solver. Two aspects 360
360 should be taken into account about the jacobian. 361

³Note that the numeration employed to formulate the dif-
ferent components does not have to match the numeration
employed for the full model. See Appendix A for more de-
tails.

362 First, it is an optional output, so that it does 412
 363 not have to be returned if it does not have an ana- 413
 364 lytical expression or the latter is too tedious to be 414
 365 derived. Instead, it is computed by finite differences 415
 366 during the simulation, although this operation re- 416
 367 sults in a significant increase of the computational 417
 368 cost. Hence, the jacobian should be provided as a 418
 369 second output when possible. 419

370 Secondly, the computation of the jacobian is nor- 420
 371 mally very expensive, but it will not always be re- 421
 372 quired by the equations solver. Therefore, this op- 422
 373 eration should be avoided when not necessary. 423

374 3.2. I2D subroutine

375 The computation of the dependent variables in 425
 376 a node (e.g. h, s, γ) from the independent vari- 426
 377 ables at that node (e.g. m, p, T and gas compo- 427
 378 sition) through a determined gas model is carried 428
 379 out by the *I2D* (independent-to-dependent) *subrou-*
 380 *tines*. The I2D subroutines may invoke for this pur-
 381 pose other specialized libraries, such as Cantera [35]
 382 or REFPROP [36]. It is possible to define as many
 383 I2D subroutines as desired, each one for different
 384 gas models or invoked libraries.

385 An I2D subroutine receives, as inputs, a vector,
 386 \mathbf{x}^{in} , with the values of the independent variables;
 387 a cell array, $\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*$, with the parameters of the func-
 388 tion—such as the employed units, the species that
 389 compose the gas and the [set of thermodynamic vari-](#)
 390 [ables selected as independent](#) ($(p, T, x_i), (h, s, y_i),$
 391 [etc.](#))—; and a cell array, \mathbf{v}^{out} , which indicates the
 392 dependent variables that are to be computed—e.g.,
 393 $\mathbf{v}^{\text{out}} = \{\text{'rho'}, \text{'h'}\}$ for density and enthalpy—.

394 The first output of the I2D subroutine is a vec- 429
 395 tor, \mathbf{x}^{out} , with the values of the variables indicated 430
 396 in \mathbf{v}^{out} . The second, which is optional and will not 431
 397 always be required, provides the jacobian of \mathbf{x}^{out} 432
 398 with respect to \mathbf{x}^{in} . As happened in the case of 433
 399 the components' residuals, it is convenient to re- 434
 400 turn the latter output argument when required— 435
 401 otherwise, the main routine of the simulator will 436
 402 compute the jacobian by finite differences, resulting 437
 403 in an increase of the computational cost— and to 438
 404 avoid its (generally expensive) computation when 439
 405 not required. 440

406 3.3. Info routines

407 For each component's residual subroutine, there 442
 408 is a *component's info subroutine* which receives the 443
 409 array $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ of parameters and returns a structure whose 444
 410 fields provide the necessary information for the as- 445
 411 sembling of the full model, such as the name of the 446

variables at each node of the component, their upper 412
 and lower boundaries, the number of equations 413
 imposed by the component's residual, etc. 414

Identically, each I2D subroutine is associated 415
 with an *I2D info subroutine* which receives the ar- 416
 ray $\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*$ of parameters of the function and returns 417
 a structure containing the necessary data for the 418
 assembling of the model. 419

The details of those structures are not to be spec- 420
 ified here since they are not important for the com- 421
 prehension of the simulation and the parameters' 422
 estimation schemes. In any case, they can be de- 423
 duced “on the go” by the interested programmer. 424

425 3.4. Summary of inputs and outputs

For the sake of clarity, the different inputs and 426
 outputs of the above mentioned subroutines are 427
 summarized in table 3.

Subroutine	Inputs	Outputs
Component's residual	$\mathbf{x}^{\text{nod}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}$	$\mathbf{f}, \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{f}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{nod}}} \right]$
Component's info	$\boldsymbol{\lambda}$	information structure
I2D	$\mathbf{x}^{\text{in}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}^*, \mathbf{v}^{\text{out}}$	$\mathbf{x}^{\text{out}}, \left[\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{out}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{in}}} \right]$
I2D info	$\boldsymbol{\lambda}^*$	information structure

Table 3: Inputs and outputs of the main subroutines. The brackets denote optional arguments.

429 4. Simulation scheme

430 4.1. Description of the algorithm

The simulation algorithm is divided in four main 431
 steps that are detailed in figure 2. The first one 432
 comprises the input of the data concerning the full 433
 gas turbine model (components, nodes, I2D func- 434
 tions, boundary conditions, etc.) and the equations 435
 solver. The second step carries out the assembly of 436
 the system of equations of the full model. This en- 437
 compasses, principally, the assignation of independ- 438
 ent and dependent variables to each node (with 439
 the aid of the info routines), and the construction 440
 of the *full system residual*—i.e., a function that 441
 receives a vector with the system unknowns and 442
 returns a vector with the residuals of all the com- 443
 ponents and general boundary conditions—. In the 444
 third step, the solver finds out the values of the 445
 unknowns that make the full system residual equal 446

to zero and, finally, the results are returned to the user.

In our case, we have considered that the unknowns of the system, \mathbf{x}^{unk} , are those independent variables whose values are not directly imposed by the fixed boundary conditions. From \mathbf{x}^{unk} , the full system residual (and its jacobian, if required) can be computed as schematized in figure 3. First, \mathbf{x}^{unk} and the fixed boundary conditions are merged into a single vector, \mathbf{x}^{ind} , with the values of all the independent variables. Next, the dependent variables, \mathbf{x}^{dep} , are computed from the independent ones by calling the I2D functions, and \mathbf{x}^{ind} and \mathbf{x}^{dep} are merged into a vector \mathbf{x}^{all} . From \mathbf{x}^{all} , the residuals of the components and of the general restrictions are evaluated and merged into a single vector, \mathbf{f}^{all} , which represents the residual of the full system. When performing these steps, the matrices of derivatives

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{dep}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{ind}}}, \quad \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}^{\text{all}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{all}}}$$

can also be obtained, either by the component's residual and the I2D subroutines (if they do return these matrices) or by finite differences (otherwise). These matrices allow the computation of the jacobian \mathbf{J} of \mathbf{f}^{all} with respect to \mathbf{x}^{unk} through the chain rule, that is,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J} &= \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}^{\text{all}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}}} = \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}^{\text{all}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{all}}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{all}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{ind}}} \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{ind}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}}} = \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial \mathbf{f}^{\text{all}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{all}}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{dep}}}{\partial \mathbf{x}^{\text{ind}}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{I} \\ \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (1) \end{aligned}$$

The computation of the jacobian (and that of the matrices above) is very expensive, although it is not always required by the solver, but only at some iterations. Therefore, this operation should be avoided when not necessary.

It is also important to remark that the jacobian and the matrices that appear in equation (1) are sparse. In effect, the restrictions imposed by a particular component (or general boundary condition) are related only to the unknown variables associated to that component (or that condition). Thus, the terms of the jacobian corresponding to that restriction and to the rest of variables are null. Taking this fact into account may lead to an important reduction in memory usage and to a significant increase in the solver's efficiency.

4.2. On the use of quasi-Newton solvers

The schemes that may be more efficient for solving the nonlinear system $\mathbf{f}^{\text{all}}(\mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}}) = \mathbf{0}$ are the so-called quasi-Newton methods [33], which compute \mathbf{x}^{unk} following an iterative algorithm of the form

$$(\mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}})^{n+1} = (\mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}})^n + \mathbf{p}^n, \quad (2)$$

where $(\cdot)^n$ refers to the n -th iteration and \mathbf{p}^n is defined by the system

$$\mathbf{G}^n \mathbf{p}^n = -(\mathbf{f}^{\text{all}})^n, \quad (3)$$

with \mathbf{G} an approximation to $\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}})$ that depends on the employed method.

Instead of directly solving the system (3) by inverting the matrix \mathbf{G}^n , which is a common practice in gas turbine simulation, selecting an appropriate numerical method can significantly reduce computation times [39]. In this case, \mathbf{G}^n is sparse and nonsymmetric, so we can solve the system with direct methods based on LU decomposition⁴ or with iterative methods such as the generalized minimal residual [40] and the biconjugate gradient stabilized [41] ones.

Most of the simulators employ the Newton-Raphson algorithm, which recomputes the jacobian at each iteration —i.e., assumes $\mathbf{G}^n = \mathbf{J}((\mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}})^n)$ —. Thus, it is very robust to poor starting guesses but very expensive at the same time. To overcome this inconvenient, some authors [31] have employed the modified Newton method, which keeps \mathbf{G}^n constant —equal to the jacobian at the first iteration, $\mathbf{J}((\mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}})^0)$ — and hence is less robust but much less expensive, not only because it avoids the recomputation of the jacobian, but also because it allows the factorization of \mathbf{G}^n to be reused⁴ in the resolution of the system (3).

Other authors [14, 16, 27] have also considered the Broyden [33, 42] algorithms. In the so-called Broyden's "good" method, \mathbf{G}^n is updated so that it verifies the "secant" condition

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{G}^{n+1} \mathbf{p}^n &= (\mathbf{f}^{\text{all}})^{n+1} - (\mathbf{f}^{\text{all}})^n, \\ \mathbf{G}^{n+1} \mathbf{q} &= \mathbf{G}^n \mathbf{q} \quad \forall \mathbf{q} \perp \mathbf{p}^n. \end{aligned}$$

⁴In the literature, it is often said that the LU factorization is the most appropriate. However, it should be emphasized that, for sparse matrices, the most appropriate factorization is the LU one with rows and columns permutations and row scaling [39].

Figure 2: Pseudocode with the main steps of the simulation scheme. Again, brackets denote optional arguments.

524 Unluckily, the resulting updating formula —refer to 545
 525 [33, 42]— does not preserve the sparsity pattern of 546
 526 \mathbf{G} , and converts it into a full matrix. This is a very 547
 527 strong disadvantage from a computational point of 548
 528 view, especially when the number of equations is 549
 529 large, because it requires to reallocate memory for 550
 530 the non-zero numbers, and moreover because it in- 551
 531 creases the degree of coupling among the equations. 552
 532 In other words, when the jacobian is sparse, an un- 553
 533 known only affects to a few equations. However, 554
 534 when the jacobian is full, an unknown takes part in 555
 535 all the equations, and then the system is much more
 536 difficult to solve. Thus, not preserving the sparsity
 537 pattern may lead to numerical instabilities.

538 On the other hand, the Broyden’s “bad” method
 539 follows a similar procedure, but directly works with
 540 the inverse of \mathbf{G} , allowing hence for a fast resolution
 541 of the system (3). However, \mathbf{G}^{-1} is a full matrix,
 542 which requires much more memory to be stored
 543 than \mathbf{G} , especially when the number of equations is
 544 large. In addition, by working with the inverse, it

indirectly destroys the sparsity pattern of \mathbf{G} , and
 therefore it may lead to numerical instabilities, as
 reported by Visser [14].

However, there are many other quasi-Newton
 solvers [33] that could be interesting for our pur-
 poses but, to best of our knowledge, have not re-
 ceived any attention in the literature, as is the case
 of the so-called *Schubert’s method* [32], which is an
 extension for sparse jacobians of the Broyden’s good
 method [33, 42]. In this scheme, each row \mathbf{g}_i of \mathbf{G}
 is updated as

$$(\mathbf{g}_i)^{n+1} = (\mathbf{g}_i)^n + \frac{(f_i^{\text{all}})^{n+1} (\hat{\mathbf{p}}_i^n)^T}{(\hat{\mathbf{p}}_i^n)^T (\hat{\mathbf{p}}_i^n)}, \quad (4)$$

556 where $\hat{\mathbf{p}}_i^n$ is the vector that results from making
 557 $p_j^n = 0$ when the corresponding component G_{ij}^n
 558 equals zero. Typically, \mathbf{G}^0 is taken as the jaco-
 559 bian at the starting guess, $\mathbf{J}((\mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}})^0)$. Note that
 560 formula (4) preserves the sparsity pattern of \mathbf{G} . By
 561 updating the approximation to the jacobian at each

Figure 3: Chart flow of the simulation algorithm. $(\mathbf{x})_N$, $(\mathbf{x})_C$ and $(\mathbf{x})_R$ are the components of the vector \mathbf{x} that correspond, respectively, to the variables defined at the node N , to the nodal variables of the component C and to the variables involved in the general boundary condition R . Idem with $(\mathbf{A})_{N,N}$, $(\mathbf{A})_{C,C}$ and $(\mathbf{A})_{R,R}$ for a matrix \mathbf{A} .

iteration, the method typically needs less iterations to converge than the modified Newton's and is also more robust to poor starting guesses. At the same time, the updating formula (4) requires very little computational effort at each iteration, so that the Schubert's method remains as competitive as the modified Newton's.

We should also point a family of methods developed by Martínez [43] that, although have not been considered in this work, could be suitable for our purposes. These schemes directly update the matrix factorization of \mathbf{G} —without destroying its sparsity—, and hence allow for a fast resolution of the system (3). We refer the reader to [33, 44] for more information about quasi-Newton methods for sparse nonlinear systems.

The main disadvantage of quasi-Newton methods with respect to the Newton-Raphson is their lower robustness against poor starting guesses. To alleviate this drawback, those methods are sometimes restarted at every k iterations (with $k \simeq 7$, typically), that is, $\mathbf{G}^n = \mathbf{J}((\mathbf{x}^{\text{unk}})^n)$, for each n multiple of k .

An important issue in all the above mentioned methods is that the vector \mathbf{x}^{n+1} may violate its upper/lower bounds if computed from equation (2). This is certainly an inconvenient if there is any routine (such as Cantera or any other software to compute the thermodynamic properties) that returns an error when it receives non-physical values of pressure or temperature as input arguments. To overcome this drawback, we have employed the reflective technique described by Coleman and Li [45], in which the borders of the hypercube formed by the upper and lower bounds act as a mirror so that, when a component x_i^{n+1} is out of its bounds (say $l_i < u_i$), it is recursively replaced by

$$\begin{aligned} u_i - (x_i^{n+1} - u_i), & \quad \text{if } x_i^{n+1} > u_i, \\ l_i + (l_i - x_i^{n+1}), & \quad \text{if } x_i^{n+1} < l_i. \end{aligned}$$

In those cases, equation (4) has to be substituted by the more general formula [46, 47]

$$(\mathbf{g}_i)^{n+1} = (\mathbf{g}_i)^n + \frac{[\Delta f_i - (\mathbf{g}_i)^n \Delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i] \Delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^T}{\Delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i^T \Delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i} \quad (5)$$

where

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta f_i &= (f_i^{\text{all}})^{n+1} - (f_i^{\text{all}})^n, \\ \Delta \hat{\mathbf{x}}_i &= (\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i)^{n+1} - (\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i)^n, \end{aligned}$$

being $\hat{\mathbf{x}}_i$ the vector obtained from making $x_j^{\text{unk}} = 0$ when the corresponding component of G_{ij}^n equals zero.

It has to be pointed out that the above mentioned reflective technique was developed for optimization algorithms and not for equations solvers. However, the formulation is somehow equivalent in both cases, since optimizing a scalar function $F(\mathbf{x})$ is the same as solving $\nabla F(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}$. Moreover, as pointed in [31], there is little information in the literature about how to deal with box-constraints when approaching the resolution of nonlinear equations, and this technique has proved, in practice, to be very efficient and robust.

Finally, it is important to remark that quasi-Newton methods need an initial guess of the unknowns, which must be relatively close to the final solution in order to achieve convergence. Usually, experience is enough to determine the expected values of the solution, and thus a “good” initial guess. When this is not the case, metaheuristic methods [48] such as genetic [49] and differential evolution [50] algorithms can be employed to produce a good approximation to the solution.

5. Parameters identification

5.1. Main idea

The algorithm described in the previous section allows to compute the variables in the gas turbine given an adequate set of boundary conditions and the values of the characteristic parameters of the different components—such as the compressor's nominal pressure ratio and efficiency—. However, those parameters are not accurately known in general, due to the lack of specific information of the equipment or even to deviations with respect to their nominal behaviour. Since the information usually available consists of large operation data sets, it is therefore necessary to develop valid procedures to determine the system parameters from those batches of data.

The most common procedure [7, 8, 10, 34, 51] is as follows. For a given set of trial values of the parameters, a simulation is performed and the deviations between predicted and real values of the gas turbine variables is quantified in terms of an objective function. Then, the trial values of the parameters are updated—following a nonlinear optimization algorithm— so as to minimize the objective function. This has the disadvantage of needing

to perform a simulation for each set of trial values of the parameters, which results in a high computational cost. However, as it is shown hereafter, this inconvenient can be avoided by an adequate selection of the objective function.

In effect, let us assume that we know the values of the nodal variables of a component at M different operation points, $\mathbf{x}_1^{\text{nod}}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_M^{\text{nod}}$. If the data and the model were perfectly accurate, it is clear that the vector of characteristic parameters $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ would verify

$$\sum_{i=1}^M |\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_i^{\text{nod}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})|^2 = 0.$$

However, the condition above is not likely to occur in practice, so we have to consider instead the value of $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ that minimizes the functional

$$S(\boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \sum_{i=1}^M |\mathbf{W}\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_i^{\text{nod}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})|^2, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{W} is a given weighting matrix used to adjust the relative importance of the different components of $\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_i^{\text{nod}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})$. As it can be seen, this objective function can be readily computed by using the component's residual routine and without having to perform a simulation of the full gas turbine. The sought value of $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ can be obtained with optimization methods such as Levenberg-Marquardt [52], nonlinear conjugate gradient [53] or BFGS [54].

Also, note that the latter definition of S allows that the parameters identification be performed component-by-component, since the residual \mathbf{f} of a certain component does not depend on the parameters of the other ones. Therefore, if the gas turbine has N_c components, it is necessary to solve N_c (uncoupled) optimization problems. In the usual procedure, however, all the parameters of the gas turbine components have to be determined at the same time, leading to only one optimization problem, but which has a bigger number of unknowns and is fully coupled (i.e., all the variables in the objective function depend on all the unknown parameters), and which is therefore much more difficult and computationally expensive to solve.

There are a few programming issues. First, if M is large, the computation of $S(\boldsymbol{\lambda})$ by means of a loop can be too time-consuming. This can be avoided if the components' subroutines are modified so that, instead of accepting a vector \mathbf{x}^{nod} and returning a vector of residuals \mathbf{f} , they receive a matrix \mathbf{X}^{nod} with M nodal vectors and return a matrix \mathbf{F}

with the corresponding residuals computed through a vectorized formulation, without the use of internal loops. Secondly, if some of the nodal variables are not known from the batch data —as it is the case for the auxiliary, non-physical variables β, ν of the compressor—, then S can no longer be written as a function of $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ only, as stated in equation (6). The latter issue is addressed in the next paragraph.

5.2. Parameters estimation with unknown nodal variables

Some nodal variables are not necessary to calculate the parameters of a given component. For example, as shown in Appendix A, the enthalpy at the inlet of the expansion turbine does not affect the equations that involve its parameters K_t, η_t . Thus, if that enthalpy were unknown, we could give it arbitrary values and proceed as usual.

However, if the unknown variables do influence the parameters estimation (e.g., the compressor's auxiliary variables β, ν), we need to proceed in a different way. In these cases, we can consider that $\boldsymbol{\lambda}$ is not the only unknown to be computed, but also the unknown nodal variables at each measure of the batch, which we will denote by $\mathbf{x}_1^{\text{nod,u}}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_M^{\text{nod,u}}$, and calculate them all by minimizing the functional

$$S(\mathbf{x}_1^{\text{nod,u}}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_M^{\text{nod,u}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) = \sum_{i=1}^M \left| \mathbf{W}\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_i^{\text{nod,k}}, \mathbf{x}_i^{\text{nod,u}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda}) \right|^2, \quad (7)$$

where $\mathbf{x}_1^{\text{nod,k}}, \dots, \mathbf{x}_M^{\text{nod,k}}$ denote the known nodal variables at each measure of the batch.

It is important to remark that, in these cases, the number of unknowns is of the order of M , which is expected to be large in order to achieve a precise estimation. Hence, the methods which require to numerically compute the hessian of S , such as [55, 56], can become tremendously slow unless the hessian sparsity pattern is taken into account. In effect, it can be readily seen from (7) that the hessian, $\mathbf{H}(S)$, presents the following sparse, block structure

$$\mathbf{H}(S) = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_1^{\text{nod,u}} & \dots & \mathbf{x}_M^{\text{nod,u}} & \boldsymbol{\lambda} \\ * & & & * \\ & \ddots & & * \\ & & * & * \\ * & * & * & * \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{x}_1^{\text{nod,u}} \\ \vdots \\ \mathbf{x}_M^{\text{nod,u}} \\ \boldsymbol{\lambda} \end{bmatrix},$$

and thus requires $O(M)$ evaluations of S to be numerically estimated, and not $O(M^2)$ as in the case of a full matrix.

It is important to remark that the unknown nodal variables that influence the parameters estimation must be auxiliary, non-physical ones, such as β and ν in the compressor. Physical variables such as pressure, temperature and mass flow, are assumed to be known since, otherwise, the parameters estimation would be infeasible from a physical point of view.

5.3. Selection of the weighting matrix

For brevity, we define $\mathbf{f}_i \triangleq \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}_i^{\text{nod}}, \boldsymbol{\lambda})$, with N the number of components of \mathbf{f}_i , and assume, without loss of generality, that \mathbf{W} is square and diagonal. Then, S reads as

$$S = W_{11}^2 \sum_{i=1}^M f_{i1}^2 + \dots + W_{NN}^2 \sum_{i=1}^M f_{iN}^2. \quad (8)$$

In general, the components of \mathbf{f}_i are measured in different units and thus are not of the same order of magnitude. Then, if all the W_{ii} are of the same order and there is a component f_{ik} that is orders of magnitude greater than the rest, we would be minimizing

$$S \simeq W_{kk}^2 \sum_{i=1}^M f_{ik}^2,$$

which would be equivalent to adjusting only the k -th restriction of the component, disregarding the other ones.

Hence, the matrix \mathbf{W} has to be chosen in such a way that all the terms in the sum of equation (8) are of the same order. Additionally, we can impose that those terms be dimensionless, so that the final result does not depend on the employed units. If these conditions are verified, any definition of \mathbf{W} could be adequate, remaining then as a subjective decision. In our case, the procedure described hereafter yielded satisfactory results.

Let us consider, for example, the case of the expansion turbine. According to Appendix A, this component imposes $4+n_S$ restrictions, being n_S the number of species through the turbine, but only the second and the third are related to the turbine's parameters K_t, η_t . Thus, we can first choose $W_{ii} = 0 \forall i \neq 2, 3$ so that the contribution of the other restrictions on S is cancelled. On the other hand, the expressions for the second and the third restrictions

(say f_2 and f_3) particularized for the i -th measure of the batch are

$$\begin{aligned} f_{i2} &= m_{i1} \sqrt{T_{i1}} - p_{i1} K_t, \\ f_{i3} &= p_{i1}^{\frac{\eta_t}{\gamma_i - 1}} T_{i2} - p_{i1}^{\frac{\eta_t}{\gamma_i - 1}} T_{i2}. \end{aligned}$$

By giving typical values to K_t and η , we can compute the expected variances of f_2 and f_3 , and define

$$W_{22} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(f_2)}}, \quad W_{33} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\text{Var}(f_3)}},$$

so that the terms $W_{22}^2 f_{i2}^2$ and $W_{33}^2 f_{i3}^2$ in equation (8) are dimensionless and of the same order of magnitude ($O(1)$).

Note that the computation of the weights can be performed automatically with the aid of the component's info —indicating in which equations the parameters take part— and of the component's residual subroutines. After a first estimation has been carried out, the user can iteratively modify the weights to get a better adjustment of certain equations (in general, the higher a weight is, the better its corresponding equation is adjusted in detriment of the others).

5.4. Parameter's estimation algorithm

The algorithm for the estimation of unknown parameters can be summarized in the following steps:

- Define input data: component's name, matrix with the values of the known nodal variables, names of the parameters to be adjusted, a starting guess for these parameters, etc.
- Compute weights as indicated in section 5.3 and define function S to minimize as in sections 5.1 and 5.2.
- Call optimization algorithm to estimate component's parameters.
- Output results. Optionally, modify the weights and go to previous step.

6. Application and validation

For validation purposes, we have applied the method to the gas turbine engine of a real combined cycle power plant in Spain, whose nominal operation point is detailed in table 4 and in reference [4]. The model employed for this turbine is represented in figure 4, and includes the inlet bleed

as shown in table 5, the most notable exception being the turbine inlet temperature (TIT), which is very high to be directly measured. The compositions of the air at the inlet and of the fuel are also known. The uncertainties in the measurements are expected to comply with the limits specified in some standards (see table 3 in [57] and table 4.1 in [58]), and are generally very low ($< 1\%$) in comparison with the corresponding nominal values.

Node	Measurands
10	m, p, T , composition
20-24	m, p, T
26,28	α
30	m, p, T
31	m, p, T , composition
40	p
41	p, T
50-52	—
60	m, p, T

Table 5: Measured variables in the gas turbine.

The measurements provided by the sensors are collected through the PI software using a piecewise linear compression algorithm [59], which also adds some uncertainties to the data. Nevertheless, these are still very low ($< 0.5\%$) when compared with the corresponding nominal values.

From the data of the measurands in table 5 and using Cantera software [35], we compute other variables of interest such as the TIT —by performing an energy balance in the combustion chamber—, the enthalpies at each point of measurement, the power absorbed/extracted by the compressor/turbine, and the gas cycle power. Note that, for this purpose, some assumptions about the behavior of the gas turbine have to be done —e.g., the TIT is computed imposing perfect energy conservation in the combustion chamber—, and thus the uncertainties can be greater for these variables than for those in table 5. Although these uncertainties are difficult to quantify, they are not expected to exceed 1% of the nominal values of the corresponding variables.

With the procedure above, we have collected the data that corresponds to a selection of days in which the gas turbine operated either close to its maximum power or close to its *environmental technical minimum* —i.e., the minimum power at which the emissions restrictions are met—. Then, the data corresponding to a specific day have been employed

to first identify the values of the components' parameters as described in section 5. The results obtained for the particular case of the compressor are illustrated in figure 5, which compares the estimated corrected mass flow, $\mu_c = m\sqrt{T}/p$, pressure ratio, PR_c , and polytropic efficiency, η_c , with the experimental values. As it can be seen, the correspondence between estimated and real values is excellent. Note that those estimated values are not constant, but depend on the parameters of the compressor and on its operation point, which are computed following the procedure described in section 5.2.

Figure 5: Values of μ_c , PR_c and η_c normalized with the manufacturer's nominal values $\mu_{c0} = 10185 \text{ Kg}\cdot\text{K}^{0.5}/(\text{s}\cdot\text{bar})$, $PR_{c0} = 16$ and $\eta_{c0} = 0.85$. Solid lines correspond to the estimated results after performing the parameters identification, circles correspond to real operation data.

To check the reliability of the model, the parameters so calculated have been used to simulate the operation of the gas turbine in the rest of selected days —characterized by different loads and ambient conditions—. In order to demonstrate the versatility of the method, the simulations have been performed twice: (i) assuming imposed values for the fuel mass flow rate and for the IGV angle, and (ii) imposing specific values to the total power output and to the EGT or to the TIT, depending on the operation point⁵. Note that (i) corresponds to a case of known actuators positions and unknown operation point, whereas (ii) corresponds to a case of known operation point and unknown actuators positions. In all the simulations, the cooling and the IBH mass flow rates were known and imposed

⁵We have tried to emulate the gas turbine control laws, which impose a fixed value to the EGT or to the TIT depending on the required power output. See [4] for more details.

910 as boundary conditions, as well as the ambient con- 934
 911 ditions, the fuel pressure, temperature and compo- 935
 912 sition and the regime speed. 936

913 To describe the gas turbine performance, we have 937
 914 focused in the following variables: (i) compressor 938
 915 inlet and fuel mass flow rates; (ii) compressor outlet 939
 916 and turbine inlet pressures; (iii) compressor outlet, 940
 917 turbine inlet and turbine outlet temperatures; (iv) 941
 918 output power; and (v) IGV angle. This particular 942
 919 choice of variables is due to the fact that, except 943
 920 the TIT and the power output, these are directly 944
 921 measured, with good accuracy, whereas others (e.g., 945
 922 the polytropic efficiencies of the compressor and of 946
 923 the turbine) must be estimated from other opera- 947
 924 tion parameters. The TIT and the power output, 948
 925 on the other hand, have been considered since they 949
 926 provide valuable information of the gas turbine ope- 950
 927 ration point. In addition, the above mentioned 951
 928 variables are also unknowns in the numerical simu- 952
 929 lations, and thus the numerical solver directly pro- 953
 930 vides their expected values. 954

931 Figure 6 shows the results obtained for imposed 955
 932 values of the fuel mass flow rate and of the IGV 956
 933 angle. As it can be seen, the agreement with the 957

experimental data is very good, especially for the 934
 variables at the compressor and for the turbine in- 935
 let pressure. The highest discrepancies are found 936
 for the turbine inlet and outlet temperatures, but 937
 are always below the 1% and the 2.5% relative, re- 938
 spectively. 939

On the other hand, figure 7 illustrates the results 940
 computed for given values of the power output and 941
 of the EGT or the TIT. Of course, the prediction of 942
 the temperatures is better now, but this does not 943
 alter the good agreement of the rest of variables 944
 with the experimental data. The main discrepan- 945
 cies are now found for the IGV angle, but are below 946
 the 3% relative. 947

It is important to remark that the above pointed 948
 discrepancies for the TIT, for the EGT and for the 949
 IGV angle are not due to imprecisions in the numer- 950
 ical procedure, but to the uncertainties in some of 951
 the variables obtained from the plant data —such 952
 as the TIT and the power output— and also to the 953
 fact that the real maps of the compressor and of 954
 the turbine are not available, and thus have to be 955
 approached by generic ones [4, 13]—. 956

Finally, figures 8 and 9 compare the performance 957

Figure 6: Variables in the gas turbine normalized with their nominal values for given fuel mass flow rate and IGV angle. The solid lines correspond to the results of the simulation and the circles to experimental data. In the legends, “C” refers to the compressor and “T” to the turbine.

Figure 7: Variables in the gas turbine normalized with their nominal values for given power output and TIT/EGT. The solid lines correspond to the results of the simulation and the circles to experimental data. In the legends, “C” refers to the compressor and “T” to the turbine.

958 of the different solvers by showing, for each of 980
 959 them, the variation of the accumulated computa- 981
 960 tion time and iterations with the number of simu- 982
 961 lations. The modified Newton and the Schubert 983
 962 methods are almost two times more efficient than 984
 963 the Newton-Raphson—which is, by far, the most 985
 964 common choice in previous works—, despite need- 986
 965 ing more iterations to converge. This is due to the 987
 966 fact that these iterations are much less expensive 988
 967 than those of the Newton-Raphson since they avoid 989
 968 the computation of the jacobian. In the figures, it is 990
 969 also seen that the performance of the modified New- 991
 970 ton and of the Schubert’s methods are very similar. 992
 971 However, the Schubert’s method has been found in 993
 972 this work to be, in general, much more robust to 994
 973 poor starting guesses.

974 7. Conclusions and future developments

975 In this work, a numerical scheme for steady- 1000
 976 state thermodynamic analysis of gas turbines is pre- 1001
 977 sented. As usual in the literature, the method is 1002
 978 based on modelling the gas turbine as a set of in- 1003
 979 dividual components—with their own equations— 1004

connected through nodes, providing then great flex-
 ibility to modify the gas turbine model and to in-
 clude new, self-defined components. However, the
 method presented here also gives similar flexibility
 for (i) the definition of new thermodynamic prop-
 erties models, so that it is possible to implement
 and choose different models that could suit better
 for a specific purpose—high accuracy, lower com-
 putational cost, etc.—; (ii) the selection of an ap-
 propriate nonlinear solver—which depends on the re-
 quired robustness and efficiency—and the inclu-
 sion of new ones into an extendable library; and
 (iii) the definition of the boundary conditions, be-
 ing possible to impose any kind of relationship
 between any variables at any nodes.

995 Another relevant feature is the possibility of iden-
 996 tifying the components’ parameters from a batch
 997 of operation data by means of a general proce-
 998 dure, also valid for components represented by a set
 999 of coupled, nonlinear equations, such as the com-
 pressor. As done in many references, this task is
 accomplished by minimizing an objective function
 with optimization techniques. However, the objec-
 tive function has been formulated here so that (i)
 its evaluation does not require to perform a full

Figure 8: Comparison of the total CPU time for different solvers: Newton-Raphson (NR), modified Newton (MN) and Schubert's method (S).

Figure 9: Comparison of the number of iterations for different solvers: Newton-Raphson (NR), modified Newton (MN) and Schubert's method (S).

gas turbine simulation and (ii) it allows to perform the parameters identification on a component-by-component basis. These aspects simplify the optimization search procedure and make it computationally more economic.

Particular attention has been given to the numerical and mathematical aspects, in order to optimize computational resources and processing time. The Schubert's method, which apparently has not been applied before in this context, has demonstrated significantly superior performance than the Newton-Raphson one, which is the most employed algorithm in gas turbine simulation. In addition, it has been found to be generally more robust than the modified Newton's, which is used by some authors. A novel approach has been also applied in order to always respect the upper and lower bounds of the variables when iterating, demonstrating that the reflective technique by Coleman and Li [45] is a very efficient and robust option. Finally, memory usage and computational efficiency can be greatly

improved if the sparse structure of the jacobian — in the simulations— and the hessian —in the parameters estimation— is taken into account. In summary, the method has been formulated so that it exploits the full capabilities of today's computers and mathematical techniques. However, at the same time, it remains simple enough to be readily implemented by the interested researchers with the aid of general-purpose mathematical computing software such as Matlab.

The actual capabilities of the simulator for practical applications have been evaluated for a real gas turbine. Using as input data only the operational variables recorded in the power plant during routine operation, the model was used, first, to estimate the parameters of each of the components of the plant and, then, to predict the behavior in different situations, including part load or variable ambient conditions. The excellent agreement obtained confirms the viability of the method for the analysis of real plants.

The calculation procedure described here is intended as a general framework that can be extended and adapted to other plant configurations or component models. In particular, work is in progress to implement more detailed compressor and turbine models (stage-stacking) for the evaluation of advanced control strategies based on the regulation of compressor extractions and gas turbine cooling flows.

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Appendix A. Equations of the components in figures 1 and 4

This appendix describes the equations used to model the different components of the gas turbine

1073 engines included in figures 1 and 4. Note that, for
 1074 the sake of generality, the components' nodes do not
 1075 follow the numeration employed for the full model,
 1076 but one that depends exclusively on the considered
 1077 component.

1078 *Compressor.*

Figure A.10: Scheme of the compressor.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1 &= m_2 - m_1, \\
 f_2 &= m_1 \sqrt{T_1} - p_1 \mu_c(\alpha_4, \beta_5, \nu_5), \\
 f_3 &= p_2 - p_1 PR_c(\alpha_4, \beta_5, \nu_5), \\
 f_4 &= T_2 - T_1 PR_c(\alpha_4, \beta_5, \nu_5)^{\frac{\bar{\gamma}-1}{\eta_c(\alpha_4, \beta_5, \nu_5) \bar{\gamma}}}, \\
 f_{4+i} &= (x_{S_i})_2 - (x_{S_i})_1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \\
 f_{5+N} &= W_3 + m_1 h_1 - m_2 h_2, \\
 f_{6+N} &= \nu_5 \sqrt{T_1} - \frac{N_3}{(N_3/\sqrt{T_1})_{design}},
 \end{aligned}$$

1079 where $\bar{\gamma} \triangleq (\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)/2$, S_1, \dots, S_N are the species
 1080 through the compressor, and μ_c , PR_c and η_c are
 1081 obtained through a compressor's map as a func-
 1082 tion of the IGV angle, α_4 , and two auxiliary co-
 1083 ordinates, β_5 and $\nu_5 \triangleq N_3/\sqrt{T_1}/(N_3/\sqrt{T_1})_{design}$,
 1084 following the procedure described in [4, 13].

1085 *Combustion chamber.*

Figure A.11: Scheme of the combustor.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1 &= m_2 - m_1 - m_3, \\
 f_2 &= p_2 - p_1(1 - \Delta p/p), \\
 f_3 &= m_2 h_2 - m_1 h_1 - m_3 h_3, \\
 f_{3+i} &= \sum_{j=1}^{N_1} a_{i,j}^1 (x_{S_j^1})_1 m_1 + \dots \\
 &\quad \sum_{j=1}^{N_2} a_{i,j}^2 (x_{S_j^2})_2 m_2 + \sum_{j=1}^{N_3} a_{i,j}^3 (x_{S_j^3})_3 m_3, \\
 i &= 1, \dots, N_2,
 \end{aligned}$$

1086 where $\Delta p/p$ is the (known) relative pressure loss,
 1087 $S_1^k, \dots, S_{N_k}^k$ are the N_k species through node k , and
 1088 $a_{i,j}^k$ is the coefficient of influence of S_j^k on the mass
 1089 balance of the specie S_i^2 that leaves the combustion
 1090 chamber.

1091 *Choked expansion turbine.*

Figure A.12: Scheme of the expansion turbine.

$$\begin{aligned}
 f_1 &= m_2 - m_1, \\
 f_2 &= m_1 \sqrt{T_1} - K_t p_1, \\
 f_3 &= p_1^{\frac{\eta_t \bar{\gamma}-1}{\bar{\gamma}}} T_2 - p_2^{\frac{\eta_t \bar{\gamma}-1}{\bar{\gamma}}} T_1, \\
 f_{3+i} &= (x_{S_i})_2 - (x_{S_i})_1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \\
 f_{4+N} &= W_3 - m_1 h_1 + m_2 h_2,
 \end{aligned}$$

1092 where $\bar{\gamma} \triangleq (\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)/2$ and S_1, \dots, S_N are the species
 1093 through the turbine.

1094 *Power meter.*

Figure A.13: Scheme of the power meter.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= W_1 - \eta_m W_2 + W_3, \\ f_2 &= N_3 - N_1, \\ f_3 &= N_3 - N_2, \end{aligned}$$

1095 where η_m is the (known) mechanical efficiency of
1096 the shaft.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= m_2 - m_1, \\ f_2 &= m_1 \sqrt{T_1} - p_1 \alpha_3 K_{\max}, \\ f_3 &= h_2 - h_1, \end{aligned}$$

$$f_{3+i} = (x_{S_i})_2 - (x_{S_i})_1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N,$$

1113 where K_{\max} is the maximum valve choke constant
1114 and S_1, \dots, S_N are the species through the valve.

1097 *Pressure loss in a duct.*

Figure A.14: Scheme of the pressure loss in a duct.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= m_2 - m_1, \\ f_2 &= \rho_1 p_2 + K (m_1)^{2-n} - \rho_1 p_1, \\ f_3 &= h_2 - h_1, \\ f_{3+i} &= (x_{S_i})_2 - (x_{S_i})_1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \end{aligned}$$

1098 where S_1, \dots, S_N are the species through the duct,
1099 and K and n are two parameters used to de-
1100 scribe the pressure loss in the duct, which is of the
1101 form $\rho_1(p_1 - p_2) = K (m_1)^{2-n}$. It can be shown
1102 that, in case of neglecting the variations of the
1103 gas viscosity with the temperature, the latter re-
1104 lation is equivalent to the more common equation
1105 $(p_1 - p_2) / (\rho_1 v_1^2) \propto (Re_1)^{-n}$ (being v_1 the velocity
1106 at the inlet and Re_1 the Reynolds number based
1107 at the inlet properties). However, the relation used
1108 here does not require to know the values of the area
1109 and of the diameter of the duct, which appear im-
1110 plicitly in the computation of v_1 and Re_1 but are
1111 usually not accurately known.

1112 *Choked valve.*

Figure A.15: Scheme of the choked valve.

1115 *Flux splitter.*

Figure A.16: Scheme of the flux splitter.

$$\begin{aligned} f_1 &= m_2 + m_3 - m_1, \\ f_2 &= p_2 - p_1, \\ f_3 &= p_3 - p_1, \\ f_4 &= h_2 - h_1, \\ f_5 &= h_3 - h_1, \\ f_{5+i} &= (x_{S_i})_2 - (x_{S_i})_1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \\ f_{5+N+i} &= (x_{S_i})_3 - (x_{S_i})_1, \quad i = 1, \dots, N, \end{aligned}$$

1116 where S_1, \dots, S_N are the species through the ducts.

1117 *Flux merger.*

Figure A.17: Scheme of the flux merger.

$$f_1 = m_3 - m_1 - m_2,$$

$$f_2 = p_2 - p_1,$$

$$f_3 = p_3 - p_1,$$

$$f_4 = m_3 h_3 - m_1 h_1 - m_2 h_2,$$

$$f_{4+i} = \sum_{j=1}^{N_1} a_{i,j}^1(x_{S_j^1})_1 m_1 + \dots$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N_2} a_{i,j}^2(x_{S_j^2})_2 m_2 + \sum_{j=1}^{N_3} a_{i,j}^3(x_{S_j^3})_3 m_3,$$

$$i = 1, \dots, N_3,$$

where $S_1^k, \dots, S_{N_k}^k$ are the N_k species through node k , and $a_{i,j}^k$ is the coefficient of influence of S_j^k on the mass balance of the specie S_i^3 of the mixture.

Note that the equations of the components above have been written so as to avoid fractions with variables in the denominator. This is done to prevent singular jacobians, and also to speed up the convergence of the quasi-Newton solvers. For instance, if K is a fixed constant, a linear equation such as $p_2 - K p_1 = 0$ is verified after the first iteration, and its derivatives never go to infinity. However, the equation $p_2/p_1 - K = 0$, which is equivalent, needs more iterations to be satisfied and its derivatives can induce instabilities if p_1 is close to 0.

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